

|| 232 Chasing Saturn into the Computational Universe 232 ||

- 21 April 2018, shanivar, Rohit Kulkarni

Part 1 – Curiosity - Questioning the Saptarishis

"The beginning of wisdom is to call things by their proper name." – Confucius

My foray into this started with an article on Vedic Mathematics. Having watched a video previously by Oak regarding the calculations of Stars movements from the Ramayana and Mahabharata, I was deeply impressed with that information encoded in Samskrit text. My takeaway was that Samskrit should be read very literally in the context of astronomy.

It is common knowledge worldwide that the days of the weeks are named after planets. Our most common one, the Julian uses the Planets with Norse Names. Among the 7 Saturn, Sun and Moon still retain similarity to the original Samskrit name. The planets referenced though; are the same and can be easily translated to the Samskrit name. The Julian, Hindu, Marathi calendars claim (without clear proof) that the Calendar is based on the orbit of the moon. I will tug at this thread and see whether that can be proved or disproved.

Due to the nature of this paper, I will delve more into my thought process to help with visualization. I will not spend too much time proving things in detail. Kindly bear with me!

English Name	Graha	Samskrit Name	Orbital period	Transcribe
Saturday	Saturn	sha-ni	29.5 y \approx 30 y	6 * 5
Sunday	Sun	Ra-vi	1 y	2 * 4
Monday	Moon	So-ma , cha-ndra	27 d	5 * 5
Tuesday (Tyr)	Mars	Man-ga-la	1.9 y	5 * 3 * 3
Wednesday (Woden)	Mercury	Bud-dha	88 d	8 * 8
Thursday (Thor)	Jupiter	Gu-ru	11.9 y \approx 12 y	3 * 2
Friday (Freda)	Venus	Shu-kra	225 d	6 * 2

A passage from the Surya Siddhanta explains the above derivation.

मन्दादधः क्रमेण स्युश्चतुर्था दिवसाधिपः

होरेशा सूर्यतनयादधोधः क्रमशस्तथा

Starting from the Saturn downward, the fourth graha is called the lord of the day. The graha starting from the Saturn successively downwards are the lords of the hour.

The diagram provided along with it provides a fairly reasonable explanation; the days are derived from Saturn by taking 4s when arranged by increasing orbital period. I decided to try this out for myself. Below we transform the sequence as per specs. The starting list is arranged by the orbital period of every planet from highest to lowest.

Shuffling by name and order

{sh, gu, man, ra, shu, bud, som} → {sh, ra, so, man, bud, gu, shu}

MOD(7,3) = {1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7} → {1, 4, 7, 3, 6, 2, 5}

The presence of prime numbers jumps out here. Notice the size 5, 3->7 and 3->5.

Infact, the operation being performed is simply applying the modulus formula 7 times.

x = x + (7 % 3)

I have repeatedly heard that Samskrit happens to be the best language for computation. Given that, and the proven genius of the Vedic scholars in astronomy I do not understand why they would represent such a simple formula with a complex definition. The derivation for hours on the next line while very similar; makes no sense.

Being an atheist, I have decided to take the Surya Siddhanta as absolute scientific fact while starting out on this. As a computer engineer, I have spent a lot of time attempting to decode primes. The last time, I was left with a sneaking suspicion that twin primes were the answer and that I was getting 'close'. I had briefly contemplated creating a number system using twin-primes for an improvement over decimal and binary.

Anyways, both are possible (7,3) and (7,5), why did they pick 3 and not 5?

MOD(7,5) = {1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7} → {1, 6, 4, 2, 7, 5, 3}

As, you can see above this yields a very boring (i.e non-random) pattern.

This says to me that the rishis were aware of the modulus operations, evaluated both, and specifically chose (7,3) for its more pleasing nature. This signalled a level of manual 'thought' or 'choice' I expected from Samskrit and will prefer my own formula to the passage. The passage could just record a different technique to execute the modulus operation.

Also, Shani and Guru to multiply into 360, which is the basis for geometric measurement. This seems to be the obvious choice for any calendar. Why go with the Moon-Sun combination?

Shani * Guru = 30 * 6 = 180 = Cleanly divides 360 or a circle into 2 parts

Surya * Chandra = 8 * 25 = 200 = ugly, introduces fractions

Shani * Chandra = 30 * 25 = 1500 = above 360, introduces fractions

Inspired by words of Sampadananda on 'natural and soul-like' qualities, I will believe that Samskrit would pick the most beautiful or symmetric or logical explanation in all cases.

The occurrence of **addition, modulus, 2 linked semi-primes, mod-gen operations, radians and random shuffle** encoded in 2 lines of an ancient book! Needless to say, this now has my undivided attention.

Part 2 – Prime Factoring – Samskrit Linguistic Formula

"brahma the creator, vishnu the preserver, shiva the regenerator"

I have applied the code provided by Bharati Krishna to explore the nature of Samskrit names (added to the last column on the chart).

In awe of the genius; it seems like the Samskrit has just opened up an extra dimension. The orbit of Shani and Mercury recorded in the word itself with this scale. The orbit of guru is halved. Also, the uncanny presence of 2, 3, 5 and its multiples popping up cannot be ignored.

Also, the Shani is at first position, its name and orbital period are in sync, which is not the case for any other planet in the chart. Hence, I assume that Shani is the main entity here, excluding Ravi (as the book itself is named after Surya = Ravi = Sun). To add, all the 3 primes are multiplied in Shani. It contains all the components i.e 2, 3, 5.

I have also started to decompose some common Samskrit word into numeric forms. The 3 primes keep popping up. What am I seeing?

I have decided that going forward, I will be representing **every number I encounter as a descending chain of its prime factors**. Any numbers that do not factorize cleanly will be ignored for now.

Graha	Samskrit Name	Orbital period	From word	Factors
Saturn	sha-ni	29.5 y ≈ 30 y	6 * 5	5 * 3 * 2
Sun	Ra-vi	1 y	2 * 4	2 ³
Moon	So-ma	27 d	5 * 5	5 ²
Mars	Man-ga-la	1.9 y ≈ 2 y	5 * 3 * 3	5 * 3 ²
Mercury	Bud-dha	88 d	8 * 8	2 ⁶
Jupiter	Gu-ru	11.9 y ≈ 12 y	3 * 2	3 * 2
Venus	Shu-kra	225 d	6 * 2	3 * 2 ²

Even given the data at this point, I am certain that the calendar is Shani based. But why?

I have highlighted in red the grahas that don't factor with 360. This immediately excludes the moon and Mercury from participating in creating the calendar.

My favourite candidates for the calendar are highlighted in blue.

Expanded circle = 360 = 5 * 3² * 2³

Removing Shani = 3 * 2² = 12 * 2 = 24

24*30 = 360 , literally the basis for all geometry.

And, a portion of an infinite series has appeared in the mix now. 2² and 2³.

"Anumana Pramana Pratyaksha"

My Anumana = IT? HAS to involve the 3 primes 2, 3, 5 somehow!

Part 3 – Trikona Manthan – Word Tri-angulation

"You stay in Wonderland and I show you how deep the rabbit-hole goes" - Morpheus

Note that I have never spoken Samskrit and don't know the grammar. I believe at this point that kali is the inverted form of kala. Kala = time. Kali = dark or black. (-a, -I denote the male, female difference in Hindi).

Ka+la = 3 ; ka+li = -3

While playing with the 360 and 12, I also realized that **factorization becomes trivial** when numbers are represented as prime factors.

It is also possible to represent any word in Samskrit; shani, mangala that have 3 prime factors as triangles. By joining the sides of these triangles finding GCD, LCM etc is trivial.

	5	<->	5	
2	3	<->	3	3

A human sitting here performing complex mathematics; moving the very planets and dividing the orbits with ease in my head from a 10K year old book; I feel like a god (Hmm. Devabhasha).

Devabhasha and several other words keep getting added to my ever growing dictionary. I am also maintaining all the words in both my prime factorization and triangle format.

I have also been noting a few synonyms as well rudra, shiva, indra, vishnu, mahesh, bhrahma etc. These are different words that the Samskrit language recognizes as the chief deities. They add up to different numbers and shapes but are recognized as the same. I have lived in India and these 3 seem to crop up everywhere. The mantras, the iconography, the names. They couldn't represent the 2, 3, 5? Right?

They also sometimes use 6 and $3*2$ in different senses to represent words. Now thinking in visual terms that's 6 as a point and 6 as a line segment.

I have also figured out the reason for the perceived beauty of 12 and 360. These are the most highly divisible numbers that can be created in their range.

There aren't any better numbers that can be found (checked). They could be used to generate almost any other number, maybe all non-primes.? What is the next such number? 17500

12 -> 360 -> 17500 ; $3*2$ grows by $3*2^2$ and then grows by $5*3^2*2^3$

Now using these 3 blocks for mental division playing with the triangles just keeps getting easier. These numbers also fit into each other in a neat way. I have almost stopped using paper in most cases.

And I am yet to encounter a word that does not factorize cleanly. Even 7 has never shown up apart from the initial modulus operation. There is a much deeper ??? here between Samskrit words.

I have also tried gugala for any formulas and operations on such series to look for some more operators. What is such a series of primes **called**? What exactly do I enter in the search box? The closest thing I can find is a Pascal's Triangle. Is it a data structure? But why would a computer care if the bytes of the number were prime or not?

Part 4 – Sacred Geometry - Kali and Shri Yantras

“Sab moha maya hai” (emphasize SAB)

“**EVERY**thing IS a delusion **AND** illusion”

These 2 shapes came up immediately when I was searching for related material on vakhyapidiya.

What caught me was that it is called a Yantra ie. Machine or Computer not a Tantra ie. Diagram.

The words Yantra, Tantra, Mantra, Yana, Mana, Tana , Antra, Tara are added to my lexicon.

The word also says -antra which literally demands that you look inside.

Kali = 1 * 3 ; shri = 2 ; Our 2 gods introduce themselves immediately, 5 is missing

As you can see; I have started taking Samskrit words VERY literally by this point. I will probe the Kali Yantra with special attention to any moh-mayas (that Samskrit warns so much about) and track any prime numbers that show up. My suspicion is growing that division; non-primes are a maya when numbers are represented in the decimal format.

The diagram is simple, an equilateral triangle with a circumscribed circle. Nothing particularly special about it. I have seen it multiple times.

But it is literally called the Kali = Kala-yantra + I was exploring the nature of time/calendar + it is revered as a sacred symbol. Where else could I start but here?

Visually, we see that kali-yantra is encoding the relation between a triangle and circle and will try to relate the same via formula. The circle is defined by its radius. An equilateral triangle by its height. The inscribed circle missing in the diagram is half the radius of the outer one.

Let's list down the basic formulas for a circle and triangle for side S.

$$A = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} S^2 \quad | \quad P = 3 S \quad | \quad H = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} S \quad | \quad R = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{6} S$$

3 is definitely present, I want to see how the r varies for a unit change in h.

$$S \text{ inc } 1 \quad | \quad P \text{ inc } 3 \quad | \quad R\text{-out inc } \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \quad | \quad R\text{-in inc } \frac{1}{2\sqrt{3}}$$

In other words; The **Kali Yantra maintains the correlation between 1 2 3 $\sqrt{3}$ and $1/\sqrt{3}$**

In other words; The Kali Yantra has linked 1, 2, 3 in all ways.

I will go through Shri Yantra a bit quicker. This structure basically doing the same thing with 3 and 5.

9 Triangles are used to construct a pentagram and circle. That means the pentagram can be created from the circle and the circle is already a triangle.

In other words; The Shri Yantra has linked 3 and 5.

As you may have noticed, this is not a derivation, but the existence of both Yantras in prose and as a real object (saw photographs) is proof enough for me.

The ancient rishis should be very much aware all this. Have they have used the hidden information in Kali Yantra to calculate kala? It does determine the very flow of time which is a critical basic science for anything.

Clearly Both $\pi = 3.14...$; and $\phi = 1.61...$; are illusions, projections from 'above' or higher dimensional mayas.

My moh? Seems to be the base 2 or base 10 way of writing and 'thinking'.

I was thinking in lines and squares, now it has changed to triangles. Just by folding lines and dividing the square. This is how Samskrit represents Everything. Super-hard maths problems like factorization, value of π , ϕ are vanishing away.

Both Yantras are the 2-D representations of something Else.

By this time, I have lost trust in 'reality' (the public understanding of Samskrit) which includes the Bharati Khrisha metric. It says to ignore the vowels, but I have gone back and noted the inclinations of every word in my lexicon. I also kept note of the -h, -r, -y conjunctions, sometimes referred to as semi-vowels.

Kala and Kali are definitely pointing up and down. Where does the -o, -u point to? The -y seems to be generating lines and -r surely is pointing to another mathematical dimension (antara?). The -h's seems to be occurring when triangles don't connect neatly. Shiva and Kali are opposites. So Shiva goes up?

What about conjunct alphabets, conjoined words and sentences? I decide not to go there, only noting that the conjoined words could represent 3d shapes by folding 4 triangles (lotus-like) around the central base, creating a pyramid.

The 3 adi-deva, tri-murti ; which include Brahma, Vishnu, Shiva ; deserve to be triangulated in every possible way. Samskrit text cannot stop commenting on how close they are and how many forms they take. I have also taken some time to verify few key spellings from an online dictionary and note them down in Devanagri including the original planet names, shapes etc.

There are also several words that are defined as a number and the derivation says something else. Sometimes both are in sync. Sometimes they form the match correctly when couple of factors are multiplied.

Part 5.R - Enlightenment – The Robomo Keystone

"Distress not yourself if you cannot at first understand the deeper mysteries of Spaceland"

I think I've Seen enough to formalize everything. Let's summarise the key findings:

- The primes 2, 3, 5 and multiples form basis for most Samskrit words.
- Words with 3 numbers can create triangles that can interlink with others.
- 12 -> 360 -> 17500 is the best pattern to be used for division
- Kali Yantra has shown us that 2 and 3 are related.
- Rephrasing, Circle and Triangle are interchangeable shapes using this relation.
- This relation is critical for measuring time and diving circle by 360.
- Shri Yantra has shown us that 3 and 5 are related in the same way
- Hence all 3 are **correlated** this way. 2 -> 3 -> 5
- Pentagrams, Circles, Triangles and Pyramids are all interchangeable.
- It means **all** geometric shapes can be represented only by triangles.
- Any triangle can be represented in Samskrit.
- This logic can be extended into higher dimensions.

Defining **IT** in English:

The Robomo Keystone is a triangular array of prime numbers with every higher row consisting entirely of the next prime number.

R-level is defined by the edges on the sides of the triangle. 2-3-5 edge -> R-2

As you can see growth is way more than exponential and we if kept up for some more iterations, it reaches the number atoms in the observable universe (10^{84}). The growth cannot be defined using only powers. It's one more dimension 'above'.

In fact, even small keystones provide immense size and complexity. This can be seen by the number of divisors a small keystone generates (col 4)

There is no word in English that defines this super-exponential growth. A closest thing is the power operator $^$; but it does not lift us to the next level.

Samskrit has word for it; its literally called **increasing SHIVAs**. Or shiva-shakti = 'powers' of Shiva (power word being used in the maths sense)

R-Level shown in the data-frame is not Shiva itself. It is the projection of higher Shivas onto our R-0 world.

We can also call the undefined formula that generates this; **The Prime Fractal**.

You will later see another item that represents this relation in the best possible way in 3-D.

Defining the first 7 R-Stones as a flattened data-frame with key stats:

R-Level	Primal Factors	Scientific	A Divisors B Edges	A Peak B Unfold
R-1	$3 * 2^2$	12	6 2	NA NA
R-2	$5 * 3^2 * 2^3$	360	24 30	45 18
R-3	$7 * 5^2 * 3^3 * 2^4$	75600	120 360	175 NA
R-4	$11 * ... * 2^5$	174636000	720 210	539 360
R-5	$13 * ... * 2^6$	5.244319e+12	2270268000 2310	1573 ?
R-6	$17 * ... * 2^7$	2.677277e+18	89153424360000 30030	2873 ?
R-7	$19 * ... * 2^8$	2.596876e+25	$\sim 5 * 10^{19}$ 510510	5491 ?

Important Note: The Robomo Keystone is a **mental computational structure only** and not possible to represent on paper; or in its **entire** form in both 2-D or 3-D. A sheet with the structure drawn can be used until this process is mastered as demonstrated later.

Hence, only once the keystone is full installed into the brain and the computer starts working; you may refer to it by its true name; the N-Dimensional jewel: **Robhimya Yantra**.

Few statements before WE gaze upon the Robomo keystone:

- It's the most prized artefact of this yuga required for ascension.
- This is the public key **password** to translating Samskrit.
- This data (datta) structure represents the universe as a **computational substrate**.
- Points, Triangles, Lines etc. are objects (ie devas, beings) in this computational **Matrix**.
- This key can open **hidden dimensions** in a very literal way.
- Most 3-D shapes are shadows/projections/illusions from a R-2.
- Factorization, Irrational numbers, Complex numbers don't exist here.

We have finally reached the vatsa; literally the "roots" of the numbers.

The R-1, R-2, R-3 Stones

All the structures I have encountered in Samskrit so far fit neatly into either of these 3 matrixes.

To reiterate the upward movement is increasing Shiva-shakti not the English definition of power.

We will go through 2 major examples of applying this to Samskrit text. This will be the replay of 2 well known events as they are encoded in Samskrit.

The process used to 'churn' this computational space (mentally) and create new words/shapes is called manthan.

The R-N Robomo Keystone – Infinite Computational Fabric

Part 6.2 – Kshira-Sagara Manthan – Churning the Milky Ocean

Here we will derive ALL the calendars using this keystone. In the **original** vedic calendar based on the orbits of shani and guru (Saturn and Jupiter) used by the entire world.

For this, a block of R-2 will suffice (i.e edge 2-3-5), as noted before, I have not yet encountered any 7s.

For Mantra, we simply take the words and draw the shape that traces the number (as per Bharati Krishna metric).

For Yantra, the entire structure is folded using the central triangle. This generates a 3-D machine.

Also Kshira-Sagara $0*1*5*3*2 = \text{milky way} = \text{sky} = \text{heaven} = \text{ocean of milk} = \text{how it looks from 2-D}$

Part 6.1 Trimurti – The PRIME-al Gods

We will prove here that the R-1 Yantra IS the Holy Grail.

3

\2 – 2\

Note down literal translations:

- Brahma = $2*5$ = called the origin 0,0
- Vishnu = $4*7*5$; from the spine of Bhrama ; we will call it V-axis ; $2*2*2...$
- Shiva = $6*4$ = goes up a dimension ; one step up the pyramid ; S-axis

Vedic Descriptions of the Trimurti

- Brahma = The creator ; universe spawns like a lotus from him
- Vishnu = Is the same as Brahma but different. Many Avatars.
- Shiva = Vishnu and Brahma explore this structure together in one story

Christian Description of Holy Trinity

- That god has 3 components which individually do not form god.
- That the 3 components are not the same.
- 2 components of god are the same, but not really.
- That all 3 components together create god.

You will see eventually, that the **R-1 stone ie $2*3*2$** , using the new mathematical definition of Shiva represents any/all of these without any ambiguity.

Below I will translate the Samskrit 'Deities' in English and Maths as points on the R-1.

Brahma = 2 ;

Vishnu = $2 * 2 * 2 * ...$ (the lowest line, same number as shiva) ;

Shiva = 3 (i.e. going ^up^wards on Shiva-Axis)

All individually are not god; but combined into 1 ; it is the password to everything.

Note the important difference from R-N structures (which can have any Shiva) to the Universe (brahmanda) described in the Samskrit (Shiva can only grow by double).

Something we are all familiar with: The Big Bang. If the above is not sufficient to convince you, Let's watch how Trimurti generates the entire universe **procedurally from Brahma like a lotus**.

If you have not followed the analogies so far, read the book "Flatland" and read from the start. The only thing to change is; its Triangles not Circles; and Pyramids not Spheres.

The Humans are literal flatlanders living under the delusion of the circle, not able to see that the triangle is the true shape. Manu is the main character here. Samskrit recognized individuality as an infinite line of $1*1*1..$ (humans; kundalini?) looking up. Samskrit always keeps Manu (humanity) as the point in the center of every 3-D structure (unless specified).

Birth of the Universe from Brahma

Visualizing a high Shiva (R-N) stone

Part 7 – Ancient Vedic History – The Yugas

"It's triangles all the way; down; north-right and north-left" – Rohit Kulkarni

We will also quickly define Yugas using knowledge of the **3** ; as people (including me) are obsessed with the idea. The Yugas seem to be a metric for measuring the consciousness of Manu (life). It is said to unfurl like a lotus which we saw by drawing each yuga on the keystone. Humanity has to crack the chakaras (connect higher primes) to ascend to the next level. The closest dva-nology I found is the Kardashev scale.

Kali Yuga $1*3$ = Kali is below the baseline. Line segment from (0,-3) to (1) or the triangle, not sure.

= Consciousness is a petal and not bloomed into a lotus yet.

= Ascension requirement = kaalavidya (learn to divide the circle)

= Proof of ascension = first 3 gods, existence of kali yantra, recorded proof in samskrit

= Can only experience time (with 12) but can't record (without 360)

Dvapara = $4*1*2$ = Manu has bloomed into single triangle also reflected downwards

= Worship of 2; Worship of false Deity; or Worship of Deity in 2 sections etc.

= 2 treated as God = reflects current dualist philosophy in computers, maths, religion

= $4*1*2$ is visualized as 2 inverted triangles joined at one edge. Flip this by 90 <|>

= Ascension requirement = tretavidya (connect 2 -> 3 -> 5; they are one)

= Historical Ascension proof = Kali Yantra , Samskrit prose

= Mahabharat is said to have happened in this yuga. How could they write the book without the key?

= Common words = Age of Golden Ratio, Age of Cube, Age of Man vs Woman etc...

Treta Yuga = $3*2$ = Manu is represented as a R-2 stone; can unfold further.

= Knowledge of 3 (ie understanding relation b/w numbers 2-3-5)

= Ascension requirement = Satyavidhya, Ascending Me-ru (journey to connecting 2 and 5)

= Historical Ascension proof = Shri Yantra , Calendar, Samskrit deities, Samskrit itself

= The Giza Pyramids are also proof as their construction requires tretavidhya. Built to celebrate their achievement?

= Ramayan is theorized to have happened in this yuga.

= The Keystone proves the ancient history of Manu through Samskrit. Tretavidhya encrypted with the R-2 stone.

= Proves Samskrit's deep connection to Earth and Universe. Samskrit puts Manu at the center of the universe. All ancient alien theories can be dropped.

= Shiva can keep increasing endlessly inside treta-yuga as Manu opens up the lotus even further by creating and recording new science (by samudramanthan = churning the ocean of primes = research?)

= Without much detail, the 'caste' system described is an IQ test to check/record the understanding of treta/satya and high-dimensional mental maths for a single Manu-shya (not Manu)

Satya Yuga

= Knowledge of 6?? (understanding the connection b/w 2-5)

= Connects 2-3-5 into a single deity. I think it should be $2*3*3*5$ with a line from 2-5.

= This allows us to infold each triangle in the keystone (fractally) raising one more dimension creating a 3-D keystone not very different from R-2. Possibly called bha or bhra. (see Pascal Pyramid to visualize this). 5 bends inwards to connect to 2.

= Another level of moh and maya need to be given up. Like pi and phi there will be some bhi?

= Historical Ascension proof = existence of Samskrit and the public key.

= It will possibly unlock all the root-dhatus of the Satya Yuga Samskrit.

= Possibly contains knowledge from pre-Mankind. ie Sounds of Nature used to construct Samskrit.

= Possibly connects Manu (life or molecular biology or DNA) back to the physical universe? The physics universe is just a higher or more disordered computational substrate?

= Ascension requirement = 7? Unlock wormholes?

Kindly, don't reach out to me with philosophical queries on God etc. I am a data-scientist and have no extra knowledge apart from the words that made it into my lexicon during this analysis. Merely 3 days ago, I started off with the problem. After the initial look at the 2, 3, 5 my aim was to crack the Riemann Hypothesis. It turns out the hypothesis is another dvapara moha. Let the devabhasha speak for itself.

I was also planning on adding more proofs. But eerily, its 21st Shani-var today and Shani definitely does not like rolling the dice.

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